

H2020 Work Programme

D4.4 - E-Learning materials for the BBECs replication

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This document is the BIObec project Report on e-Learning materials for the BBECs replication (contract no. 101023381) corresponding to D4.4 (M30) led by SIE. This document contains reports about the creation of the e-learning materials based on the project outcomes and experience, with the specific aim to serve as support material for the Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs) replication.

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (JU) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101023381. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

BIC	Bio-based Industries Consortium
CBE JU	Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking
BBEC	Bio-Based Education Centre
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
SIE	Sustainable Innovations
CTA	Corporación Tecnológica de Andalucía
IRWG	Implementation and Replication Working Group
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable, D4.4 - E-Learning materials for the BBECs replication, describes the tools (design, implementation, outcome, and promotion) produced in the context of the capacity building activities of the project, as well as their further promotion. These materials have the main aim of giving guideline, ideas and inspiration for further replication of the Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs). This was developed by carefully documenting each step of the process and shows proof of all the tasks done in the last few months.

A timeline with the main three communication phases is presented, to finish with an overview of the actions carried out within the first six months of the project.

2 Introduction

2.1 Context of WP4

This work package (WP4) focuses on replicating successful practices among potential future EU Bio-Based Economy Centers (BBECs) by using knowledge from earlier project stages. The goal is to coordinate learning and collaboration, creating useful resources (such as a roadmap, or events like seminars or workshops) along the project's process. In WP4 ways to start new BBECs are explored, ensuring quality and alignment with European strategies and local approaches. Collaboration involves various entities who will use their networks at EU and international levels for successful implementation.

2.2 Objectives of Task 4.4

Task T4.4 aims to develop a comprehensive Toolkit for anyone interested in the BIObec project (and with a focus on those who could be open to replicate the BBECs experience). This will be done by offering diverse e-Learning resources to support the replication and expansion of BBECs. These tools are designed to reach multiple audiences, including educational institutions, industry professionals, regional authorities, and society at large.

These e-Learning resources will be hosted on the project website and maintained for up to two years beyond the project's completion. The primary goal is to ensure sustained access to these valuable resources, fostering continued learning and replication opportunities within the Bio-Based Economy domain.

3 BIObec's e-learning materials

3.1 BBECs Map

The first tool created in the context of this suite was a simple map where anyone can locate every BBEC and see basic information about the partners that are involved on

it, the kind of network it has, its knowledge area, the type of centre and the main value chains it specializes in. It has been created as a dynamic presentation with Genial.ly, and there is one slide for every regional BBEC. Every slide is also linked with a Youtube video where the pathway of this regional BBEC is explained (those videos are also displayed on the “Webinars & workshops recordings” section of the website, see section 3.4 of this document for further information). In figures 1, 2 and 3 below the map can be seen, as well as an example of a specific BBEC slide and an example of a video insertion in the slide.

Figure 1: BBECs' map

Figure 2: Mediterranean BBEC slide

Figure 3: Insertion of a video-frame of the Mediterranean Pathway experienceslide

3.2 Story maps

Four story maps have been created with the objective of giving an interactive source of information for anyone interested on the project's outcomes. They summarize the information contained in D4.2 (Roadmap Report for BBECs replication) and D3.3 (Report on detailed budget for running and maintaining the six BBECs and financial plans), as well as the conclusions pointed out by the BBEC leaders in the hybrid event organized by CTA in Viena on the 6th of September. 'Cross-fertilization seminar among BBECs and Roadmap co-design experience' (see section 3.4 of this document for further information).

INTRODUCTION

As this is the simplest one, [this story map](#) has been created with a different tool than the others, ArcGIS Story Maps. It is an interactive page with the appearance of a common landing page. There, users can find:

- A short introduction to the project (as seen in Figure 4).

Introduction BBECs structure Biobec's BBECs leaders location... Stakeholders

Introduction

The EU's Bioeconomy Strategy adopted in 2012 and updated in 2018 pursues **five objectives**:

- 1 Ensure food and nutrition security.
- 2 Manage natural resources sustainably.
- 3 Reduce dependence on non-renewable resources.
- 4 Mitigate and adapt to climate change.
- 5 Strengthen European competitiveness and create jobs.

Derived from the **switch to a sustainable bioeconomy**, many new jobs will be necessary. Following this, it is also necessary to start **including bioeconomy across the different education levels**.

When speaking about bioeconomy, the **different countries and regions in the EU have different levels of development**. This means that it is not possible to set only one strategy, but we need to think about what strategies are more adequate for each area.

The BIObec project aims to **develop a method that serves as a framework for Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs)**. These centres address, with a multi-level view, the present and future needs of the industry and of the surrounding ecosystem in each region.

Figure 4: First story map: Introduction

- A description of the BBECs structure (Figure 5).

Introduction BBECs structure Biobec's BBECs leaders location... Stakeholders

BBECs structure

A BBEC is an **educational centre that gives training to many different profiles having in mind the present and future challenges detected by the bio-based industries**. They have a regional scope, so they can adapt to the reality of the territory where they are located.

These bio-based education hubs:

- Integrate **various stakeholders**.
- **Promote cooperation** between those stakeholders.
- **Include bioeconomy** or bio-based economy as an essential part of their mission.
- Have a **leading role in the bioeconomy** at regional, national or international level.
- Develop education, training, research and innovation strategies, actions and activities for **any educational level**.
- Are established or emerging hubs with a **long-lasting vision and strategy**.

Figure 5: First story map: BBECs structure

- An interactive map with basic information about every BBEC, containing the same information as in the BBECs Map except from the videos (Figure 6).

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Figure 6: First story map: BBECs leaders structure

- A short description of every stakeholder that can be benefited from or get involved in the BIObec project (Figure 7).

Figure 7: First story map: Stakeholders

HOW TO DEVELOP A BIO-BASED EDUCATION CENTRE (BBEC)?

This [Story Map](#) summarizes and organizes interactively the information from the Deliverable 4.2: Roadmap Report for BBECs replication. As in the roadmap, this

document describes different maturity stages so any group can understand what point they are at in the journey to establish a BBEC. Specifically, there are five stages:

Figure 8: Second story map. Initial slide

- Preparatory Stage

Figure 9: Second story map. Preparatory stage slide

- Stage One

Figure 10: Second story map. Stage one slide

- Stage Two

Figure 11: Second story map. Stage two slide

- Stage Three

Figure 12: Second story map. Stage three slide

- Stage Four

Figure 13: Second story map. Stage four.

This is the longest of all the story maps, as it contains specific information of every stage, divided into sections (as can be seen in the figures above, there are at least two

sections for each stage). Each section also brings to more detailed information (sometimes leading the user to a new slide, as seen in Figure 14, sometimes giving information in windows or labels, as seen in Figures 15 and 16).

Figure 14: Example of a section that brings to a new slide (right) and of the slide that the user sees after clicking on the subsection (left)

Figure 15: Example of a window shown in a section's slide

Figure 16: Example of a label in a section's slide

These stages are also referenced in the auto-test (see section 3.5 of the current document), which sends the users to the different sections of this story map (as well as to the deliverable mentioned above) so they can understand any maturity stage by reading it.

FUNDING AND FINANCING OPPORTUNITIES

The third story map details all the funding and financing opportunities that can be useful for anyone who wants to replicate the BBEC experience. It is mainly based on

the Deliverable 3.3: Report on detailed budget for running and maintaining the six BBECs and financial plans. It presents separate parts for public (Figures 17 and 18) and private (Figure 19) opportunities.

Figure 17: Third story map. Public funding (part 1) slide

Figure 18: Third story map. Public funding (part 2) slide

Figure 19: Third story map. Private funding slide

All the buttons on the slides shown above bring the user to a window with basic information of the funding/financing programmes and a link to the official website (as seen in Figure 20).

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Figure 20: Window with information about a specific program

BEST PRACTICES, RISKS AND LESSONS LEARNED

This story map starts with a copy of the map created for the BBECs (Figure 21), with which the user can navigate through the different conclusions of each BBEC. The same structure is kept for information about each BBEC. In addition, there is a button for the best practices, a button for the risks and a button for the lessons learned (as can be seen in Figure 22 below). Each of them brings to a window with specific information (Figure 23).

Figure 21: Fourth story map: BBECs map

Figure 22: Fourth story map: example of a BBEC slide (German BBEC)

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Figure 23: Example of a window with information

3.3 BBECs leaders' interviews

Six interviews were conducted with the six BBEC leaders in order to provide insights into their experiences for those interested in BIObec project. The questions were formulated bearing in mind that the people who will watch those videos will have an interest in replicating the experience. It was decided to organize the interviews by question, instead of by interviewee, as it was understood that it was more useful for a user to find an answer to a specific topic rather than learning from a specific regional experience. The six questions (and video topics) are the following:

- What are the most favourable conditions for starting the creation of a BBEC?

1. Most favourable conditions for starting a BBEC - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 24: "Most favourable conditions for starting a BBEC" video caption.

- What are the most challenging aspects of the BBEC creation process?

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2. Most challenging aspects - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 25: "Most challenging aspects" video caption

- Which activities have you observed that stakeholders liked the most?

3. Stakeholders preferred activities - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 26: "Stakeholders preferred activities" video caption

- What type of training offerings do you believe will be better received by the students, based on your analysis and experience?

4. Student-Preferred Training Approaches - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 27: "Student-Preferred Training Approaches" video caption

- Why would you encourage the creation of a BBEC?

5. Encouraging the creation of a BBEC - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 28: "Encouraging the creation of a BBEC" video caption

- Could you share any positive outcomes or unexpected benefits that emerged from the BIObec project, which you may not have initially anticipated?

6. Unexpected positive outcomes - Interviewing BBEC leaders

Figure 29: "Unexpected positive outcomes" video caption

3.4 Workshops & webinars recordings

To date, seven videos containing workshops or webinars have been uploaded to the BIObec's YouTube channel, as well as to the training section of the website. The videos are recordings of live workshops that were deployed during the 'Cross-fertilization seminar among BBECs and Roadmap co-design experience', which was organized by CTA on September the 6th in Vienna, just after the project's meeting that took place on the 5th. It brought together a varied group of experts from the fields of bioeconomy and took place in the context of the [European Bioeconomy Scientific Forum 2023](#):

- [Roadmap for BBECs replication](#). Rafael Sánchez Dueñas from CTA outlines the plan created as part of the BIObec project framework. This plan provides valuable insights for individuals seeking to establish a BBEC in a different area (Figure 30).

Roadmap for BBECs replication

Figure 30: Opening for the Roadmap workshop recording

- [Danish BBEC Pathway experience](#). Jan Lund and Knud Tybirk, part of the Danish BBEC, highlight valuable insights gained during the establishment of the BBEC in this area (Figure 31).

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Figure 31: Opening for the Danish pathway recording

- Mediterranean BBEC Pathway experience. Giacomo Maria Rinaldi, leader of the Mediterranean BBEC, highlight valuable insights gained during the establishment of the BBEC in this area (Figure 32).

Figure 32: Opening for the Mediterranean pathway recording

- Central Eastern Europe BBEC Pathway experience. Tadeus Pęczek, from the Central Eastern Europe BBEC, highlight valuable insights gained during the establishment of the BBEC in this area (Figure 33).

Central Eastern Europe BBEC Pathway experience

Figure 33: Opening for the Eastern Europe pathway recording

- Irish BBEC Pathway experience. Fiona Scott-Hayward, leader of the IrishBBEC, presents the key insights drawn from the process of establishing the BBEC in this specific area (Figure 34).

Irish BBEC Pathway experience

Figure 34: Opening for the Irish pathway recording

- German BBEC Pathway experience. Lina Mayorga, leader of the German BBEC, highlight valuable insights gained during the establishment of the BBEC in this area (Figure 35).

German BBEC Pathway experience

Figure 35: Opening for the German pathway recording

- Finnish BBEC Pathway experience. Katri Rusanen and Jouni Pykäläinen, from the Finnish BBEC, highlight valuable insights gained during the establishment of the BBEC in this area (Figure 36).

Finnish BBEC Pathway experience

Figure 36: Opening for the Finnish pathway recording

Along with these videos, three more videos were uploaded in February. They are the recording of the three parts of the capacity building workshop entitled “CAPACITY BUILDING AND 2ND INTERNATIONAL IRWG WORKSHOP” that was held online on January, 22nd. (for more information D4.3). The recording of this workshop and its inclusion in the current deliverable is the main reason for requesting a delay on the submission of D4.4. This decision was taken by the leader coordinator and the Project Officer to submit complete documentation. Below are described the three videos:

- E-Learning Materials User Guide. Daniel Matilla, from Sustainable Innovations, explains in this video the entire e-learning suite displayed on the website.

BIObec - E-Learning Materials User Guide

Figure 37: Opening for the E-Learning Materials User Guide

- Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap. Rafael Dueñas, from CTA, details the pathway to replicate the BIObec methodology, providing an overview of the project's roadmap.

Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap

Figure 38: Opening for the Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap

- 2nd International Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) Workshop. Selenia Marinelli, from FVA, introduces the key exploitable assets and tools derived from the results of BIObec. These resources aim to empower members of the Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) in their efforts to replicate BIO-Based Education Centres (BBECs).

Figure 39: Opening for the 2nd International Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) Workshop

3.5 Auto-test

An auto-test has been created for anyone interested in the replication of our BBEC experience. It asks questions about the available knowledge, funding, structure, etc. that a particular group could have. Its aim is to provide the user with a maturity level, according to those established in D4.2: Roadmap Report for BBECs replication. It gives the user a “level of maturity” after answering some questions, and it refers to the specific sections on this level of both this deliverable and the “How to develop a bio-based education centre (BBEC)? Story Map”, explained in section 3.2 above. The test has been created with Typeform, an interactive tool for online tests. Some of its parts can be seen in Figure 40 below.

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Figure 40: Screen captures of different points in the auto-test

4 Implementation on the project's website

SIE has created a dedicated section on the BIObec website, called "E-learning Materials". It presents a structure in subsections, with an initial short description and access to the auto-test (Figures 41 and 42).

Figure 41: Upper part of the "E-learning Materials" section

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Figure 42: "E-learning Materials" section's submenu.

It was decided to place the auto-test at the beginning as it is a good tool for any user to be aware of his/her knowledge and maturity towards creating a BBEC. Knowing this could help the user to navigate better through the e-learning materials, as some of them can be too basic or too complex depending on the maturity stage of the user.

As mentioned above, this section has been divided into four subsections, one per type of material. The subsections are:

BBECs MAP

It presents only the BBECs Map explained in the section 3.1 of this document. It is the first subsection as it is a good starting point for understanding the basics and locate all the BBECs and their singularities (Figure 43).

Figure 43: "BBECs Map" subsection

STORY MAPS

This section shows the four story maps outlined in section 3.2 of this document. The first story map (the one made with ArcGIS StoryMaps) is displayed as an image that links to the tool. The other three are the Genial.ly presentations (Figure 44).

Figure 44: "Story Maps" subsection

BBEC LEADERS INTERVIEWS

The six videos mentioned in section 3.3 are the content for this subsection. They appear as YouTube miniatures, and can be played directly on the webpage (Figure 45).

BECs MAP STORY MAPS BBEC LEADERS INTERVIEWS WORKSHOPS & WEBINARS

1. MOST FAVOURABLE CONDITIONS FOR STARTING A BBEC

2. MOST CHALLENGING ASPECTS

3. STAKEHOLDERS PREFERRED ACTIVITIES

4. STUDENT-PREFERRED TRAINING APPROACHES

5. ENCOURAGING THE CREATION OF A BBEC

6. UNEXPECTED POSITIVE OUTCOMES

Figure 45: "BBEC LEADERS INTERVIEWS" subsection

WORKSHOPS & WEBINARS

The last section of this suite presents all the recordings explained in section 3.4 of this document. As well as in the previous section, the videos are presented as YouTube miniatures that can be played directly on the site (Figure 46).

E-LEARNING MATERIALS USER GUIDE

Introduction to the BIObec's e-learning

BIObec CAPACITY BUILDING WORKSHOP

Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BICL

2ND INTERNATIONAL IMPLEMENTATION AND REPLICATION WORKING GROUP (IRWG) WORKSHOP

2nd INTERNATIONAL

ROADMAP FOR BBECs REPLICATION

DANISH BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

IRISH BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

MEDITERRANEAN BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

CENTRAL-EASTERN EUROPE BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

FINNISH BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

GERMAN BBEC PATHWAY EXPERIENCE

Figure 46: "Workshops & webinars" subsection

5 Promotion

To increase visibility for the mentioned materials, and as a part of the project's communication strategy, SIE has created and will create different actions for the promotion of the e-learning materials. The materials will be shared on the project's official social media pages, which include X (formerly known as Twitter) and LinkedIn, as well as in the project newsletters.

To this date, and as this e-learning suite is of recent creation, only some of the materials have been promoted. Specifically, the BBEC leaders' interviews were shared in the last project's newsletter and the first interview has also been shared in the project's social media accounts (Figures 47-49).

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Would you like to know more about our BBEC's experiences? Watch now the interviews with all of our BBEC leaders

In this playlist, you will have the opportunity to learn from our BBEC leaders, who answer six different questions that are very useful for anyone thinking on replicating our experience or just learning from them. There is one video per question, answered by every BBEC leader. Here you have the first out of the six videos. If you want to navigate the entire playlist, click on the video playlist below.

Figure 47: Section on the BIObec newsletter that promotes the BBEC leaders' interviews

BIObec
743 followers
1w • Edited •

+ Follow ...

What are the most favourable conditions for starting the creation of a **BIObec** centre?
In this video, the leaders of our six Bioeconomy-Based Education Centres (BBECs) envision the ideal scenario for initiating the creation of one of these centres.

<https://lnkd.in/d63N-Tj8>

Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC) Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC) Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna University of Hohenheim University of Eastern Finland Irish Bioeconomy Foundation Munster Technological University CTA (Technological Corporation of Andalusia) Consiglio Ordine Nazionale Tecnologi Alimentari Food & Bio Cluster Denmark AgroParisTech Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona Sustainable Innovations (SIE) IHE Delft Institute for Water Education Wageningen University & Research FVA New Media Research University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU) PRO CIVIS Foundation Educational Research Institute Trakia University-Stara Zagora VÚP a ZV Troubsko

Lina Mayorga
German BBEC

1. Most favourable conditions for starting a BBEC - Interviewing BBEC...

youtube.com

Figure 48: Post on the project's Linkeding sharing the first interview

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Figure 49: Post on the project's X (former Twitter) sharing the first interview

The entire content has been shared in the project's newsletter, and will be periodically shared in the form of social media posts. Concretely, the contents are:

- In the last project newsletter, a section about the Capacity Building Seminar has been shared. There, it is also embedded the video that explains the e-learning section on the website:

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BIObec Capacity Building and 2nd Int. IRWG Workshop

Centre Readiness: Level Framework Assessment Survey

OBJECTIVE	INDICATOR	MEASURE TO FINANCIAL
Extended survey covering 22 questions around knowledge, assets, thematic plans of the organization by clusters: lecturer profiles, network links to industry, innovation, students, research, enterprise development and support agencies, research centres, vocational education centres, cooperatives and organizations, among others, within the organization in order to build structure of future BBEs.		
Development of an overarching design and achievement of projects each centre. The Centre Readiness Assessment Survey allowed the work resources and capabilities in their regions starting point from which to consider development of regional BBEs.		
		CSI - Report on completed and operational activities for BBEs at BBEs

2nd International Implementation and Replication Working Group (IRWG) Workshop

BIObec presented the online Capacity Building and 2nd International IRWG workshop, which took place on January 22nd, 2024. The online workshop had two main objectives: the transfer of the BIObec methodology for the implementation and replication of regional BBEs in other regions or countries, as well as educational contents and exploitable assets ready to be implemented by the educational community.

BIObec project

Presentation of the BIObec replication methodology through the BIObec roadmap

Introduction to the BIObec's e-learning materials
Daniel Matilla

BIObec - E-Learning Materials User Guide

Figure 50: Capacity building workshop's section in the newsletter

- In social media, at least it will (or have been) be shared:
 - A post promoting the entire “E-learning Materials” website section (Figures 51 and 52).

Figure 51: E-learning section promotion on LinkedIn

Figure 52: E-learning section promotion on X (formerly Twitter)

- One post per subsection.
- One post per BBEC leaders interview video.

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Later, it will be evaluated if sharing each of the materials is helpful for the project's dissemination and communication or not. This will depend on other actions related with the project that may be subject to be shared.

6 Conclusions

The completion of the e-learning tools and their inclusion on the project's website marks a significant milestone in the BIObec project. This comprehensive report details the creation of e-learning materials aimed at facilitating the replication of Bio-Based Education Centres (BBECs). These tools, crafted from the project's outcomes and experiences, serve as a rich repository of resources, offering guidance, insights, and inspiration for those interested in furthering BBEC replication.

The suite of e-learning resources encompasses diverse tools, including interactive presentations, insightful interviews with BBEC leaders, workshop recordings, and an auto-test assessing organizational maturity for BBEC creation. Moreover, the strategic dissemination plan outlined in this report ensures the sustained availability and promotion of these tools, fostering continuous learning opportunities within the Bio-Based Economy domain.

This deliverable stands as proof of collaborative efforts and dedication in advancing knowledge dissemination and capacity building. It sets the stage for wider accessibility and utilization of these valuable resources, paving the way for the creation and replication of BBECs and the further development of the bioeconomy sector.

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